

The Impact of Passenger Service Quality and Satisfaction Level on Performance as Mediated by Hr Professionalism in Pt Peln Year 2020

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Abstract:- Analysis of the Level of Satisfaction and Quality of Passenger Service is what will affect the Improvement of Employee Performance. So that efforts are needed to improve the performance of HR Professionalism. The research was conducted at PT Peln with the passenger of KM Dobonsolo Tj. Priok with a total sample of 150 employees. Data were collected through the instrument on a question sheet with a Likert scale model that had been tested. The data analysis method used in this study used the path analysis method or path analysis. The results of the first study, it was concluded that the level of customer satisfaction had a positive and significant effect on improving employee performance. Passenger Service Quality has a positive and significant impact on Employee Performance Improvement. HR Professionalism which has an impact on increasing Employee Performance Improvement, so that HR Professionalism as a moderating variable is proven to function to strengthen the influence of Passenger Satisfaction Level and Quality of Service on Employee Performance Improvement.

Keywords:- Customer Satisfaction, Service Quality, HR Professionalism, Performance Improvement.

I. INTRODUCTION

A maritime nation, Indonesia connects the continents of Asia and Australia and is situated geographically between the Pacific and Indian Oceans. The maritime wealth of Indonesia is made up of renewable resources such fisheries, coral reefs, mangroves, seaweed, and biotechnological goods. There are also non-renewable natural resources like oil, gas, tin, iron ore, bauxite, and different minerals. For Indonesia's maritime economic operations, ports serve as growth agents for industries like industry, trade, and tourism. Ports can be used to boost state revenue and develop into centers of commerce and social exchange.

The concern of users of crossing services is the continual development and enhancement of inter-island migration services. The Central Statistics Agency (BPS) estimates that 1.1 million domestic ship passengers will travel domestically in September 2020. This number is lower by 3.33% when compared to August 2020. The number of passengers traveling on cruise ships has declined at the ports of Belawan and Balikpapan. where the declines were, respectively, 71.73% and 1.45%. On the other hand, at Tanjung Priok Port, 33.08%, Tanjung Perak, and 32.22% in Makassar, the number of passengers climbed by 76.92%, 33.08%, and 32.22%, respectively. In January-September 2020, there were 10.6

million domestic maritime travelers, which is a 39.58% decrease from the same time in 2019.

The fluctuation in the number of sea travelers should provide room for service-quality enhancements that will satisfy customers. Regulations of PT.PELNI that charge travelers for excess baggage pose a challenge to passenger satisfaction. The mobility of other passengers might be hampered by travellers who carry too much luggage, especially when going on the KM Dobonsolo takes days. There is less room for other passengers to rest when there is more luggage than is allowed. Other passengers using marine transportation are displeased and uncomfortable as a result of this. Each passenger at KM Dobonsolo is allowed a maximum of 50 kg of checked baggage; if the customer has more than 50 kg, there will be an additional fee.

Measuring customer satisfaction is a crucial activity for the organization to perform in order to assess where it stands in relation to other crossing service providers and identify areas that might use improvement. In order to meet or surpass their consumers' expectations, shipping businesses must consistently beat their rivals. Customers will be satisfied if this is accomplished. One metric for measuring the success of the service industry is passenger satisfaction. Compared to air travel, the utilization of sea travel is still declining in terms of method of transportation.

II. RESEARCH PROBLEM

This study tries to answer the following questions:

1. Is there a direct effect of Satisfaction Level on the Performance Improvement Efforts of PT. Peln tahun 2020 (KM. Dobonsolo)?
2. Is there a direct influence of Service Quality on the Performance Improvement Efforts of PT. Peln tahun 2020 (KM. Dobonsolo)?
3. Is there a direct effect of Human Resources Professionalism on the Performance Improvement Efforts of PT. Peln tahun 2020 (KM. Dobonsolo)?
4. Is there a direct influence of Satisfaction Level on the Service Quality of PT. Peln tahun 2020 (KM. Dobonsolo)?
5. Is there a direct influence on the Satisfaction Level on Human Resources Professionalism of PT. Peln tahun 2020 (KM. Dobonsolo)?
6. Is there a direct influence on the Service Quality on Human Resources Professionalism of PT. Peln tahun 2020 (KM. Dobonsolo)?

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ *Satisfaction Level*

Customer satisfaction is the outcome of consumers' or customers' collective use of a good or service. Because of the accumulation of outcomes, customer happiness has a temporal dimension (Irawan, 2002). A person feels satisfied when performance or outcomes live up to his various expectations. A person feels satisfied when they contrast the actual results with the predicted ones (Dailiati, 2018). Quality, service, and value are three ways to satisfy customers. Customer satisfaction is a measurement of a product's qualities or features that give customers a certain amount of pleasure in relation to meeting their consumption demands (Nuralam, 2017).

According to the previously mentioned definition of customer satisfaction, it can be determined that this state is one that a person experiences after assessing the qualities or features of a good or service and determining whether it has satisfied their demands for consumption. Customer satisfaction can be raised through enhancing a product or service's quality, value, and service. In consumer behavior theory, contentment is typically defined in terms of the experience a consumer has after consuming or utilizing a good or service.

Customer expectations have a big impact on customer satisfaction, thus knowing them thoroughly and accurately is crucial when developing a customer satisfaction strategy. Customers' expectations can occasionally be managed by a business, but manufacturers frequently can't. Customer satisfaction is dynamic as a result of this.

➤ *Service Quality*

Service quality is the customer's evaluation of the service based on a comparison between the service received and the customer's expectations for the service (Hamirul & Alamsyahril, 2020). Service quality is the effort made by the business to match customer expectations. According to Mu'ah and Masram (2014), service quality highlights the level of customer satisfaction offered by the firm providing the service. The term "service quality" refers to how well a service performs, particularly when comparing dependencies in customer service encounters (Daryanto, 2013).

The description of service quality leads one to the conclusion that it is the most important variable in influencing customer satisfaction. Service quality can be regarded as customer satisfaction. When comparing the sort of service with other services that are similar, this is decided. When a service matches customer expectations, it is deemed to be of good quality; when it exceeds expectations, it is deemed to be of extremely high quality.

The goal of service quality is to increase client happiness. Regardless of how well customers respond to them, every business manager has a duty to uphold this satisfaction in line with the function of service quality and give customers a feeling of security and contentment. Customers can be happy on their second and future routine visits to their place of

business in this way. This enhances the company's reputation in the public eye.

➤ *Human Resources Professionalism*

Professionalism is the commitment of a profession's members to continually develop their abilities. Professionalism is a mental attitude that is demonstrated by how committed professionals are to maintaining and enhancing their professional excellence (Darmansah, 2020). The concept of professionalism describes how people or groups behave when they successfully adhere to certain standards. Professionalism is a set of actions, aspirations, or traits that define a profession (Egok, 2019). Professionalism is a type of responsiveness that includes the capacity to recognize community needs, set agendas, prioritize services, and create service plans based on those needs and ambitions. Professionalism is a term that describes mental attitudes and behavior, especially the commitment of professional members to continuously recognize and enhance the quality of their employees. (Pasolong, 2020).

According to the definition of professionalism given above, if it is connected to ethics, professionalism is a behavioral requirement that needs to be met in every line of employment. Whether a person is professional will affect their level of customer satisfaction and the caliber of services they offer. Professional human resources help businesses operate more profitably and provide the services that customers demand. One of the government-funded Nawacita projects places a strong emphasis on the value of qualified human resources in boosting output and community competitiveness on the global market.

➤ *Performance Improvement*

Performance is an action or activity displayed by a person to carry out specific tasks in order to attain a goal or the best possible job outcome (Setiana, 2014). When an organization performs well, it accomplishes its objectives, and this process is ongoing and continual (Saraswati, 2017). Performance is a term used to describe the degree to which an activity, program, or policy has been implemented and has contributed to the attainment of the organization's established goals, objectives, vision, and mission as described in its strategic plan (Muhdar, 2021).

Performance can be defined as the outcome of a person's work based on the quality and quantity he has achieved to support activities within an organization. Performance is then measured, and the results are used to plan the organization's strategic planning, according to the definition of performance provided above. A measure of performance is the process of gathering, examining, and communicating various data regarding the degree of performance of a person, group of people, or organization. The maintenance of a corporation depends heavily on performance measurement. To quantify it, organizations need a method that is more thorough and detailed. Here, the company or group requires Important Performance Metrics. There are a number of prerequisites for performance indicators that will be used as Key Performance Indicators, also known as SMART indicators, according to (Saraswati, 2017).

- a. Specific, Indicators must be precise, comprehensive, and focused.
- b. Measurable, The Key Performance Indicator requirements must be objectively measurable, both quantitatively and qualitatively, as KPI variables cannot generally be measured objectively if they lack a unit value.
- c. Achievable, KPI metrics ought to be attainable (achievable). This indicates that the goals must be practical and reachable.
- d. Reliable, KPIs need to be trustworthy (trustworthy). The crucial thing to remember is that KPIs might be vitally necessary for a firm to fulfill its objectives.
- e. Time bound, has a deadline for achieving the target

Performance appraisal is one part of performance management; organizations utilize a performance appraisal system akin to what organizations or businesses in general do to improve the performance of their human resources. A set of practices known as a performance management system is intended to foster a shared understanding of the objectives of the business. The process of performance planning, performance training, and performance evaluation are all included in the performance management system. It is anticipated that HR will be able to operate efficiently through the performance process to enable the accomplishment of company goals.

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses the quantitative method. The quantitative approach is a research procedure that produces data in numbers and is generally analyzed using descriptive or inferential statistics (Silaen, 2018). The numbers obtained are processed and sought to determine their effect on the formulation of the research problem that has been determined. Do the survey results prove the proposed hypothesis? Do the numbers show that we are right about the problem under study? Etc.

The passengers on board the KM Dobonsolo ship will serve as the target population for this study, with a total sample size of 150 passengers. Obtaining samples that are representative of all research subjects is done using the sampling technique. Because it describes how to select a representative sample, sampling technique is a crucial component of statistical methods.

V. RESULT

➤ *Validity Test*

The value of the critical limit of validity is 0.184. If the correlation value or r count is less than or less than 0.184, the questionnaire item is invalid. On the other hand, if the calculated r-value is greater than 0.184, then the items on the questionnaire are declared valid. Test the validity of the research instrument (questionnaire) for each of the variables studied can be seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Validity Test Result

Pernyataan	Nilai Koefisien Koreksi (r hitung)				Status
	Tingkat Kepuasan Pelanggan (X ₁)	Kualitas Pelayanan Penumpang (X ₂)	Profesionalisme SDM (Z)	Peningkatan Kinerja (Y)	
1	0.771	0.870	0.865	0.634	Valid
2	0.835	0.772	0.875	0.886	Valid
3	0.424	0.849	0.879	0.656	Valid
4	0.633	0.850	0.535	0.875	Valid
5	0.782	0.748	0.858	0.824	Valid
6	0.831	0.696	0.858	0.715	Valid
7	0.701	0.504	0.706	0.645	Valid
8	0.825	0.656	0.777	0.551	Valid
9	0.710	0.382	0.714	0.845	Valid
10	0.845	0.406	0.870	0.819	Valid

Source: Primary data, processed by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 26.

Table 1 shows that each item of each variable statement of Customer Satisfaction Level, Passenger Service Quality, HR Professionalism, and Performance Improvement are declared valid.

➤ *Reliability Test*

Table 2. Reliability Test Result

Variabel	Nilai Alpha	Nilai Batas	Status
Tingkat Kepuasan Pelanggan (X ₁)	0.908	0.70	Reliabel
Kualitas Pelayanan Penumpang (X ₂)	0.872	0.70	Reliabel
Profesionalisme SDM(Z)	0.930	0.70	Reliabel
Peningkatan Kinerja (Y)	0.901	0.70	Reliabel

Source: Primary data, processed by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 26

Table 2 shows that the overall alpha value is reliable (reliable) because the Cronbach Alpha coefficient is 0.70, or it can be said to be greater than 0.70. In accordance with the results of the validity and reliability analysis mentioned above, the statement items prepared from each variable can be used and distributed to all 37 employees who have been targeted as respondents. Therefore, it can be seen that the items show valid and reliable results. From these results, further analysis can be carried out.

➤ *Partial Test*

Table 3. Partial Test Structure 1

Model		Coefficients ^a		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		Unstandardized Coefficients	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	-14.649	3.164		-4.629	.000
	TINGKAT KEPUASAN PELANGGAN	.548	.122	.356	4.474	.000
	KUALITAS PELAYANAN PENUMPANG	.714	.111	.514	6.460	.000

a. Dependent Variable: PROFESIONALISME SDM

Source: primary data, processed by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 26

- 1) Customer Service Level (X1) has an impact on HR Professionalism (Z). When the Sig value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 or (0.00 < 0.05), the path analysis coefficient is significant, as shown by the partial individual test (partial) / t test results. This means that the degree of customer satisfaction (X1) has a favorable and considerable impact

- on HR professionalism (Z). A beta value of 0.548, or 54.80%, indicates that Customer Satisfaction Level (X1) has a direct impact on HR Professionalism (Z).
- 2) HR Professionalism is influenced by Passenger Service Quality (X2). The path analysis coefficient is significant if the value of Sig 0.000 is less than 0.05 or $[0.000 < 0.05]$ when the individual test (partial) / t test results are shown. As a result, professionalism is significantly and favorably impacted by the quality of passenger service (Z). The beta value of 0.714, or 71.40 percent, indicates that Professionalism (Z) is directly influenced by the Quality of Passenger Service.

Table 4. Partial Test Structure 2

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	30.310	2.942		10.308	.000
	TINGKAT KEPUASAN PELANGGAN	.200	.113	.213	2.172	.047
	KUALITAS PELAYANAN PENJUMPAK	.251	.109	.312	2.308	.022
	PROFESIONALISME SDM	.258	.072	.488	3.537	.001

a. Dependent Variable: PENINGKATAN KINERJA KARYAWAN

Source: primary data, processed by Statistical Package for the Social Sciences version 26

- 1) Customer Satisfaction Level has a direct effect on Employee Performance Improvement From table 4 shows that the t-test obtained a Sig value of $0.047 < 0.05$, so the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, using the Customer Satisfaction Level has a positive and significant impact on the Employee Performance Improvement. The direct influence of Customer Satisfaction Level on Employee Performance Improvement is indicated by the Beta value of 21.3%.
- 2) Quality of Passenger Service has a direct effect on Employee Performance Improvement. Table 4 shows the t-test obtained Sig $0.022 < 0.05$, then the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, Quality of Passenger Service has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance Improvement. The considerable influence of Quality of Passenger Service on Employee Performance Improvement is indicated by the Beta value of 31,4%.
- 3) HR professionalism has a direct effect on Employee Performance Improvement. Table 4 shows the t-test. The Sig value of 0.001 is smaller than 0.05 or $[0.001 < 0.05]$, so the path analysis coefficient is significant. Thus, the HR professionalism has a positive and significant effect on the Employee Performance Improvement. The considerable influence of HR professionalism on Employee Performance Improvement is indicated by a Beta value of 43,8%.

➤ Sobel Test

The Sobel test was conducted to test whether the relationship through a mediating variable could function as a significant mediator in the relationship. The calculation of the z value of the Sobel test can use the danielsoper online link via www.danielsoper.com with the Statistical Calculator → MediationModels → Sobel Test Calculator for Significance of Mediation feature, with the following results:

- 1) Mediation Test of Customer Satisfaction Level on Employee Performance Improvement through HR professionalism.

Fig 1 Sobel test model 1

Based on Figure 1 the one-tailed probability result is $0,0282324 < 0,05$, so it can be concluded that the HR professionalism variable can function as a mediator or is able to mediate the indirect effect of Customer Satisfaction Level on Employee Performance Improvement.

- 2) If Quality of Passenger Service on Employee Performance Improvement through HR professionalism.

Fig 2. Sobel test model 2

Based on Figure 2, the one-tailed probability result is $0.00102201 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the HR professionalism variable can function as a mediator or be able to mediate the indirect effect of Quality of Passenger Service on Employee Performance Improvement through HR professionalism.

VI. DISCUSSION

- H1, The level of customer satisfaction has a significant and positive effect on performance improvement. Based on the results of the analysis, the path coefficient of the Customer Satisfaction Level variable has a positive and statistically significant effect on performance, with a value of 0.200 or 20.00 percent and a significance level of 0.047. This shows that employee performance will increase in proportion to the level of customer satisfaction with their work. Thus, the level of customer satisfaction is acceptable considering the performance improvements that have been implemented..
- H2, The increase in performance is significantly and profitably influenced by the quality of passenger service. The

path coefficient of the variable Passenger Service Quality on the Performance Improvement variable is 0.251 or 25.10 percent with a significance of 0.022 according to the results of the analysis. Improving the quality of services provided to consumers is an important aspect to ensure customer satisfaction. Erni (2009) concluded from his research that service quality is an important factor in producing customer satisfaction, and good work quality will also affect good performance.

➤ □ H3, HR Professionalism has a significant and positive effect on Performance Improvement. The path coefficient for the HR Professionalism variable is 0.253 or 25.30 percent with a significance level of 0.001. It is recommended that every employee can maintain a professional attitude at work in order to maximize the skills, time, energy, knowledge and resources they have according to their field. Therefore, the professionalism of employees will affect their performance. Employees with a high level of professionalism tend to produce good results because they are able to position themselves so they can understand the tasks and responsibilities assigned.

➤ H4, The level of customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on HR professionalism. Based on the results of the analysis, the path coefficient of the Customer Satisfaction Level variable to the HR Professionalism variable is 0.548 or 54.80 percent with a significance of 0.000..

➤ H5, Passenger Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on HR Professionalism. Based on the results of the analysis, the path coefficient of the Customer Satisfaction Level variable to the HR Professionalism variable is 0.714 or 71.40 percent with a significance of 0.000..

➤ H6, HR professionalism is able to function as a mediator or mediate the influence of Customer Satisfaction Levels on Performance Improvement. This means that if HR Professionalism is in accordance with Customer Satisfaction that has been built by the company, it is able to improve employee performance, so that HR Professionals as a moderator variable are proven to function to strengthen the influence of Customer Satisfaction Levels on Increasing Employee Performance.

➤ H7, HR professionalism is able to function as a mediator or mediate the effect of Service Quality on Performance Improvement. This means that if HR Professionalism is in accordance with the Quality of Service that has been built by the company, it is able to improve employee performance, so that HR Professional as a moderator variable is proven to function to strengthen the effect of Service Quality on Employee Performance Improvement.

VII. CONCLUSION

From the results of research and overall analysis, some conclusions can be drawn as follows:

1. The level of customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on work improvement at PT Pelni..
2. Passenger Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on Work Improvement at PT Pelni.
3. HR Professionalism has a positive and significant effect on Work Improvement at PT Pelni.
4. The level of customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on HR professionalism at PT Pelni.

5. Passenger Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on HR Professionalism at PT Pelni.
6. HR professionalism is able to function as a mediator or mediate the indirect effect of the level of customer satisfaction on work improvement at PT Pelni.
7. HR Professionalism is able to function as a mediator or mediate the indirect effect of Passenger Service Quality on Work Improvement at PT Pelni

VIII. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the conclusions above, the authors provide suggestions and recommendations as follows:

1. To raise and maintain customer happiness, particularly by enhancing operational efficiency and service quality. Thus, the trust between customers who employ PT. Pelni services can be concluded.
2. It is advised to look at other factors that also have a big impact for other researchers, especially PT. Pelni, who will conduct study on passenger service quality, customer satisfaction, HR professionals, and operational performance improvement. So, it is believed that these studies would be helpful in offering feedback and recommendations to businesses and the academic community.

IX. IMPLICATION

The implications of the research findings and the above-described recommendations are that PT Pelni service quality is improving, both formal and non-formal communications can function in accordance with the goals that are governed by the business' operational standards, and the use of various communication media has been used to smooth the flow of information quickly and precisely..

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